

Studies on the Behaviour of Bivalent Salts in Aqueous Solution. Part I. Cadmium Sulphate

P. K. Jena and B. Prasad

Studies with cells using cadmium sulphate and a mixture of cadmium sulphate and potassium sulphate, with and without liquid junction potential, show the presence of Cd^{2+} , SO_4^{2-} , CdSO_4 , and $\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}$. Dissociation constants

$$\frac{a_{\text{Cd}^{2+}} \times a_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}}{[\text{CdSO}_4]} = K_1 \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{[\text{CdSO}_4] \times [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]}{[\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}]} = K_2$$

have been found to be 0.8×10^{-3} and 4.3×10^{-2} respectively at 35° from cells without liquid junction potential. A method based on the measurement of activity of sulphate with NH_4NO_3 as salt bridge is found to be fairly reliable for finding K_1 and K_2 . This study also gives an idea of the extent of elimination of the junction potential by the various salt bridges.

Davies and coworkers¹ from the studies of the dissociation of a number of bivalent sulphates by conductance method assumed the dissociation to be $\text{MSO}_4 \rightleftharpoons \text{M}^{2+} + \text{SO}_4^{2-}$ and calculated the dissociation constant. McBain and Van Rysseberg² found an appreciable amount of $\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}$ present in a mixture of CdSO_4 and MgSO_4 . The following types of cells, in which Hg_yCd_x (11-12% of Cd) represents a two-phase amalgam, were studied to throw further light.

Cells of the type (b), (c), (d), and (e) are denoted as b_1, c_1, d_1 , and e_1 , respectively when KCl is used as bridge and b_x, c_x, d_x , and e_x respectively when NH_4NO_3 is used as bridge.

1. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1927, 23, 354.

2. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 3009.

EXPERIMENTAL

Stock solutions of cadmium sulphate and potassium sulphate were prepared from A.R.(B.D.H.) salts. Their stoichiometric concentration was estimated gravimetrically as oxime and barium sulphate respectively. A stock solution of cadmium perchlorate was prepared as described previously³ and its stoichiometric concentration was determined gravimetrically as oxime. The thermostat, cell vessels, and salt bridges used, the method of preparing and checking the half elements, and the process of setting up the cells were as in earlier studies⁴. All the experiments were done in duplicate at $35^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$ and the duplicates agreed within 0.2 mv. The measured E.M.F. of the cells of the type (a) to (f) are recorded in Tables I to VI respectively. Concentrations in all the tables are given in g. moles per litre and suffix "T" indicates stoichiometric concentration.

TABLE I

Type of cell used: (a).

$[\text{CdSO}_4]_T$	E.M.F.	*E°	**E°
0.02	1.0930 volt	0.9506	0.9532
0.03	1.0889	0.9505	0.9535
0.04	1.0848	0.9505	0.9535
0.05	1.0820	0.9493	0.9528
0.06	1.0795	0.9471	0.9517
0.07	1.0777	0.9465	0.9508
0.08	1.0760	0.9452	0.9502
0.09	1.0747	0.9454	0.9499
0.10	1.0736	0.9450	0.9499

*From $\alpha_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$ (KCl)—cell b_1 and $\alpha_{\text{Cd}^{2+}}$ (KCl)—cell c_1 .**From $\alpha_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$ (NH_4NO_3)—cell b_2 and $\alpha_{\text{Cd}^{2+}}$ (NH_4NO_3)—cell c_2 .

TABLE II

Type of cell used: (b).

$(\text{CdSO}_4)_T$ as well as $(\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4)_T$	(b_1)	E.M.F. (mv.)	(b_2)	$\alpha_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$	
				KCl	NH_4NO_3
0.02	7.4	5.1	0.00468	0.00557	
0.03	8.8	6.2	0.00544	0.00661	
0.04	10.1	6.9	0.00573	0.00730	
0.05	10.7	7.6	0.00605	0.00764	
0.06	11.8	8.1	0.00601	0.00795	
0.07	12.2	8.8	0.00614	0.00805	
0.08	13.0	8.8	0.00606	0.00832	
0.09	13.2	9.3	0.00632	0.00848	
0.10	13.7	9.5	0.00633	0.00860	

3. *This Journal*, 1954, 31, 480.4. *Ibid.*, 1951, 28, 693.

TABLE III

Type of cell used: (c).

[(Cd(ClO ₄) ₂) ₂] _T as well as (CdSO ₄) _T .	E.M.F. (mv).		$a_{cd^{2+}}$	
	(c ₁).	(c ₂).	KCl.	NH ₄ NO ₃ .
0.02	8.3	8.0	0.00460	0.00470
0.03	9.2	8.8	0.00577	0.00595
0.04	10.3	9.7	0.00653	0.00683
0.05	10.7	10.2	0.00736	0.00764
0.06	11.8	11.1	0.00764	0.00811
0.07	12.3	11.5	0.00817	0.00867
0.08	13.0	12.2	0.00855	0.00908
0.09	13.2	12.5	0.00914	0.00964
0.10	13.6	12.9	0.00968	0.01021

TABLE IV

Type of cell used: (d).

(K ₂ SO ₄) _T unmixed.	Mixture of (CdSO ₄) _T , (K ₂ SO ₄) _T .		E.M.F. (mv).		$a_{so_4^{2-}}$	
			d ₁ .	d ₂ .	KCl.	NH ₄ NO ₃ .
0.06	0.02	0.04	3.2	2.2	0.01150	0.01240
0.07	0.02	0.05	2.7	2.1	0.01256	0.01314
0.08	0.02	0.06	3.5	2.9	0.01241	0.01298
0.06	0.03	0.03	5.0	3.6	0.01004	0.01116
0.09	0.03	0.06	5.0	3.7	0.01172	0.01293
0.10	0.03	0.07	2.9	2.1	0.01430	0.01519

TABLE V

Type of cell used: (e).

[(CdSO ₄) _T as well as (Cd(ClO ₄) ₂) _T].	[K ₂ SO ₄] _T .	E.M.F. (mv).		$a_{cd^{2+}}$	
		e ₁ .	e ₂ .	KCl.	NH ₄ NO ₃ .
0.02	0.04	19.5	18.8	0.00198	0.00208
0.02	0.05	20.5	20.0	0.00183	0.00190
0.02	0.06	21.8	21.4	0.00168	0.00171
0.03	0.03	17.5	16.5	0.00308	0.00333
0.03	0.06	21.4	20.5	0.00230	0.00248
0.03	0.07	22.7	21.0	0.00208	0.00221

TABLE VI

Type of cell used: (f).

(CdSO ₄) _T .	(K ₂ SO ₄) _T .	E.M.F.	-*E°.	**E°.
0.02	0.04	1.0931 volt	0.9512	0.9530
0.02	0.05	1.0932	0.9516	0.9527
0.02	0.06	1.0933	0.9503	0.9513
0.03	0.03	1.0878	0.9502	0.9526
0.03	0.06	1.0879	0.9501	0.9506
0.03	0.07	1.0880	0.9500	0.9514

*From $a_{so_4^{2-}}$ (KCl)—cell d₁ and $a_{cd^{2+}}$ (KCl)—cell e₁.**From $a_{so_4^{2-}}$ (NH₄NO₃)—cell d₂ and $a_{cd^{2+}}$ (NH₄NO₃)—cell e₂.

DISCUSSION

In cells (b) to (e) the elimination of liquid junction potential is provisionally assumed. The E. M. F. of the cells (i) 'b' and 'd', (ii) 'c' and 'e' are then given by equations (1) and (2) respectively.

$$E = \frac{RT}{2F} \log_e \frac{a'_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}}{a_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

$$E = \frac{RT}{2F} \log_e \frac{a'_{\text{Cd}^{2+}}}{a_{\text{Cd}^{2+}}} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

In the above equations (i) $a'_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$ indicates the activity of SO_4^{2-} in pure K_2SO_4 solutions, both in cells 'b' and 'd'; (ii) $a_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$, the activity of SO_4^{2-} in solutions of CdSO_4 in cell 'b' and in solutions of mixtures of K_2SO_4 and CdSO_4 in cell 'd'; (iii) $a'_{\text{Cd}^{2+}}$, the activity of Cd^{2+} in $\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ solutions both in cells 'c' and 'e'; (iv) $a_{\text{Cd}^{2+}}$, the activity of Cd^{2+} in solutions of CdSO_4 in cell 'c' and in solutions of mixtures of CdSO_4 and K_2SO_4 in cell 'e'. Cadmium perchlorate³ and K_2SO_4 ³ solutions up to 0.1 molar concentration have been shown to be completely dissociated. In this paper, it has been assumed that at ionic strength in the cells of this work (i) KCl , KNO_3 , and $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ are completely dissociated, (ii) the activity coefficient of any ion has a definite value at a fixed ionic strength, (iii) the activity coefficient of K^+ and Cl^- ions are equal in KCl solutions, (iv) the activity coefficient of Cd^{2+} in any solution is the same as that of Ba^{2+} at the same ionic strength, and (v) the difference between concentration and molality is negligible. Some of these assumptions are only approximately correct, but these are accurate enough for the concentrations in our experiments. With these assumptions, the activity coefficient (f^{2+}) of Cd^{2+} at various ionic strengths was calculated from the knowledge of the activity coefficient of KCl , KNO_3 , and $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and that (f^{2-}) of SO_4^{2-} , from those of KCl and K_2SO_4 . The activities of Cd^{2+} in cadmium perchlorate solutions and of SO_4^{2-} in potassium sulphate solutions were thus available for use in cells (b) to (e) at the ionic strengths of the solutions. The activity (i) of SO_4^{2-} in CdSO_4 solutions, (ii) of Cd^{2+} in CdSO_4 solutions, (iii) of SO_4^{2-} in solutions of mixtures of CdSO_4 and K_2SO_4 , and (iv) of Cd^{2+} in solutions of mixtures of CdSO_4 and K_2SO_4 , as calculated from the E. M. F. of the cells concerned are recorded in Tables II, III, IV, and V respectively. The bridge used for measuring the activity has been indicated by writing the name of the salt used after the activity.

The E. M. F. of the cell 'a' as well as that of 'f' is given by the equation

$$E = E^0 - \frac{RT}{2F} \log_e a_{\text{Cd}^{2+}} \times a_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

For each solution of cadmium sulphate, investigations were made with cells 'a', 'b', and 'c' and for each solution of a mixture of cadmium sulphate and potassium sulphate investigations were made with cells 'd', 'e', and 'f'. Hence it became possible to substitute the values of $a_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}(\text{NH}_4\text{NO}_3)$ or $a_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}(\text{KCl})$ and $a_{\text{Cd}^{2+}}(\text{NH}_4\text{NO}_3)$ or $a_{\text{Cd}^{2+}}(\text{KCl})$ in cells of the type, 'a' and 'f' and determine E^0 (cf. Tables I and VI). Since E^0 is not constant within

experimental limits, l. j. p. has not been eliminated in some or all the cells (*b*, *c*, *d*, and *e*) used for measuring activity of Cd^{2+} and SO_4^{2-} . The value of E° for $\text{Cd}_x\text{Hg}_y \mid \text{Cd}^{2+}$ from the work of Harned and Fitzgerald⁶ and Bates⁷ comes out to be 0.3540 volt at 35°. The value of E° for the $\text{Hg} \mid \text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4, \text{SO}_4^{2-}$ at 35° has been shown⁵ to be -0.6025 volt. Hence E° for the cell of the type '*a*' or '*f*' has been taken to be 0.9565 volt.

Let us confine our attention to cell '*a*' for the time being. Knowing E° , it becomes is possible to find $a_{\text{Cd}^{2+}} \times a_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$ for the solution concerned. In solutions of CdSO_4 , if it is provisionally assumed that there is only one equilibrium, $\text{CdSO}_4 \rightleftharpoons \text{Cd}^{2+} + \text{SO}_4^{2-}$, then $[\text{Cd}^{2+}] = [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$ in all the solutions used in cells of type (*a*). An arbitrary value is given to $[\text{Cd}^{2+}]$, the corresponding ionic strength from $\mu = \frac{1}{2} [\text{Cd}^{2+}]^2 + f^{2+}$, and f^{2-} on the basis explained earlier and thereafter $[\text{Cd}^{2+}]^2 \times f^{2+} \times f^{2-}$ are found. If $[\text{Cd}^{2+}]^2 \times f^{2+} \times f^{2-}$, thus found, differs from $a_{\text{Cd}^{2+}} \times a_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$ as found from E and E° of the cell, then $[\text{Cd}^{2+}]$ is altered till $[\text{Cd}^{2+}]^2 \times f^{2+} \times f^{2-}$ becomes equal to $a_{\text{Cd}^{2+}} \times a_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$, as found from E and E° . The concentration of Cd^{2+} , at which the expressions are equal, corresponds to the equilibrium state. The concentration of undissociated cadmium sulphate is equal to the stoichiometric concentration of cadmium sulphate minus the concentration of Cd^{2+} . The value of '*K*' where

$$K = \frac{a_{\text{Cd}^{2+}} \times a_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}}{a_{\text{CdSO}_4}}$$

is given below. It may be assumed that a_{CdSO_4} is equal to $[\text{CdSO}_4]$.

$[\text{CdSO}_4]_{\text{T}}$	..	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.07	0.08	0.09	0.10
$K \times 10^3$	..	5.47	4.10	3.37	3.13	3.07	2.94	2.84	2.72	2.61

The continuous decrease in '*K*' with increase of $[\text{CdSO}_4]_{\text{T}}$ is due to a higher complex being included in the concentration of undissociated cadmium sulphate. If a higher complex is formed, then it must be between CdSO_4 and SO_4^{2-} , giving rise to $\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}$. There may be two equilibria governing the breaking of the complexes given by the equations (4) and (5):

In cell '*a*', i.e., in solutions of cadmium sulphate, there are Cd^{2+} , SO_4^{2-} , CdSO_4 , and $\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}$. Now

$$[\text{Cd}]_{\text{T}} = [\text{Cd}^{2+}] + [\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}] + [\text{CdSO}_4] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

and

$$[\text{SO}_4]_{\text{T}} = [\text{SO}_4^{2-}] + 2[\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}] + [\text{CdSO}_4] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

Since

$$[\text{Cd}]_{\text{T}} = [\text{SO}_4]_{\text{T}} \text{ therefore} \\ [\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}] + [\text{SO}_4^{2-}] = [\text{Cd}^{2+}] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (8)$$

The ionic strength of the solution is given by

$$\mu = 2[\text{Cd}^{2+}] + 2[\text{SO}_4^{2-}] + 2[\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}]$$

which is transformed to the following form with the help of equation (8)

$$\mu = 4[\text{Cd}^{2+}] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

6. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 2424.

7. *Ibid.*, 1939, 61, 308.

The value of $a_{\text{Cd}^{2+}} \times a_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$ for each value of $[\text{CdSO}_4]_{\text{T}}$, which can be determined from E and E° with the help of equation (3), is independent of K_1 and K_2 . For any value of K_1 , there will be a definite value of $[\text{CdSO}_4]$, which can be found from equation (4). For any definite value of K_1 , after finding $[\text{CdSO}_4]$, an arbitrary value is given to $[\text{Cd}^{2+}]$ and the corresponding value of $[\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}]$, $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$ and μ are found from equations (6), (8), and (9) respectively and f^{2+} and f^{2-} from μ . From these values $[\text{Cd}^{2+}] \times [\text{SO}_4^{2-}] \times f^{2+} \times f^{2-}$ is calculated and if it is found to be different from $a_{\text{Cd}^{2+}} \times a_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$, determined from equation (3), the arbitrary value given to $[\text{Cd}^{2+}]$ is altered till there is no difference. At the stage when the difference disappears, $[\text{Cd}^{2+}]$, $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$, $[\text{CdSO}_4]$, $[\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}]$ correspond to the value of K_1 , assumed and K_2 to be calculated. The value of K_2 , corresponding to the assumed value of K_1 , is then calculated from equation (5) assuming that the activity coefficients of $\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}$ and SO_4^{2-} ions are the same at the same ionic strength and that of CdSO_4 is equal to unity. If the concentration of $\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}$ in 0.025M solution is negligible, the correct value of $K_1 \times 10^{-3}$ will be 5.47 or say 5.5, otherwise it will be higher. So 5.5, 6.0, 6.5, 7.0, 7.5, and 8.0 were assigned to $K_1 \times 10^{-3}$ and the corresponding values of K_2 were calculated. For any value of K_1 , several values of K_2 , corresponding to different concentrations, their mean $\bar{K}_2$, mean of $(K_2 - \bar{K}_2)^2$, i.e., Δ and $\Delta/\bar{K}_2$ were calculated. It was found that $\Delta/\bar{K}_2$ was lowest for $K_1 = 7.0 \times 10^{-3}$. Hence K_1 was taken to be 7.0×10^{-3} from the study of cells of type 'a'. It is possible to calculate $a_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$ and $a_{\text{Cd}^{2+}}$ by multiplying $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$ with f^{2-} and $[\text{Cd}^{2+}]$ with f^{2+} . The values are likely to be correct as no liquid junction is involved. Table VII records the value of K_2 , $a_{\text{Cd}^{2+}}$, $a_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$, thus calculated for different values of $[\text{CdSO}_4]_{\text{T}}$ when $K_1 = 7.0 \times 10^{-3}$.

TABLE VII
Values obtained from cell (a).
 $K_1 = 7.0 \times 10^{-3}$.

$[\text{CdSO}_4]_{\text{T}}$	$a_{\text{Cd}^{2+}}$	$a_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$	$K_2 \times 10^2$
0.02	0.00573	0.00565	..
0.03	0.00806	0.00618	3.99
0.04	0.00962	0.00659	3.32
0.05	0.01112	0.00706	3.44
0.06	0.01250	0.00758	3.88
0.07	0.01376	0.00787	4.16
0.08	0.01507	0.00818	4.36
0.09	0.01634	0.00832	4.44
0.10	0.01759	0.00839	4.42
			Mean 4.00

Let us now turn to cell 'f'. In these cells equations (6) and (7) hold good, but equations (8) and (9) do not and in their places we have the following equations:

Using the same methods as in case of cell 'a', except that equations (10) and (11) take the places of equation (8) and (9) respectively, the values of K_2 , corresponding to different concentrations of cadmium sulphate, and a definite value of K_1 are calculated. The values of $K_2 \times 10^2$, corresponding $K_1 \times 10^3$ being equal to 6.0, 6.5, 7.0, and 7.5, were examined as in the case of cells of the type 'a' and $\Delta/\bar{K}_2$ was found to be minimum for $K_1 = 6.5 \times 10^{-3}$. The values of K_2 , $a_{\text{Cd}^{2+}}$, and $a_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$ for different values of $[\text{CdSO}_4]_{\text{T}}$, corresponding to $K_1 = 6.5 \times 10^{-3}$, are shown in Table VIII.

TABLE VIII

Values obtained from cell 'f'.

$$K_1 = 6.5 \times 10^{-3}.$$

$[\text{CdSO}_4]_{\text{T}}$	Mixture of	$[\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4]_{\text{T}}$	$a_{\text{Cd}^{2+}}$	$a_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$	$K_2 \times 10^3$
0.02		0.04	0.00296	0.01148	3.89
0.02		0.05	0.00266	0.01266	4.26
0.02		0.06	0.00245	0.01368	4.67
0.03		0.03	0.00408	0.01018	4.00
0.03		0.06	0.00375	0.01342	5.06
0.03		0.07	0.00349	0.01428	5.37
					Mean 4.54

Taking the mean of the best values of K_1 and K_2 in the cells 'a' and 'f', K_1 comes out to be 6.8×10^{-3} and K_2 to be 4.3×10^{-2} . A comparison $a_{\text{Cd}^{2+}}$ values, shown in Table VII, with $a_{\text{Cd}^{2+}}$ values in Table III makes it abundantly clear that the values of $a_{\text{Cd}^{2+}}$ in Table III are far from correct. The same conclusion is reached with regard to $a_{\text{Cd}^{2+}}$ shown in Table V, when compared with $a_{\text{Cd}^{2+}}$, recorded in Table VIII. A comparison of $a_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$, given in Table VII, with $a_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$ in Table II shows that the error in the values of $a_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$ (NH_4NO_3) in Table II does not exceed 11% in any case, but is generally much less and almost disappears in some of the measurements. A similar comparison of $a_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$ values in Table VIII with $a_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$ values in Table IV shows that agreement is of the same order in case of both $a_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$ (KCl) and $a_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$ (NH_4NO_3). Hence it is clear that l.j.p. can be neglected for rough work in cells of the type (b) when NH_4NO_3 and cells of the type (d), when either salt is used as bridge, and it cannot be neglected in cells of the types (c) and (e).

In a large number of salts of the type MSO_4 , it is not possible to get cells of the type 'a' or 'f'. Since it is possible to get a rough value of $a_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$ with cells of the types 'b₂' and 'd₂', it may be worthwhile to calculate the values of K_1 and K_2 from the $a_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$ (NH_4NO_3) and to see the extent to which they agree with the values already determined.

Let us confine our attention to cell 'b₂' first. This cell gives a rough value of $a_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$ in CdSO_4 solutions. To begin with, we may assume only one equilibrium:

and in that case $[\text{Cd}^{2+}] = [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$. We may assign any arbitrary value to $[\text{Cd}^{2+}]$. The ionic strength will be equal to $4[\text{Cd}^{2+}]$ and corresponding to this f^{2+} and f^{2-} are known and $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$ can be found from $a_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$. If $[\text{Cd}^{2+}]$ and $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$ differ, the arbitrary value of $[\text{Cd}^{2+}]$ is altered till the two become equal. Since in this case

$$[\text{CdSO}_4]_{\text{T}} = [\text{Cd}^{2+}] + [\text{CdSO}_4]$$

it becomes possible to calculate $[\text{CdSO}_4]$ and K , i.e.,

$$\frac{a_{\text{Cd}^{2+}} a_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}}{[\text{CdSO}_4]}$$

The values of K determined in this way are given below.

$[\text{CdSO}_4]_{\text{T}}$	..	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.07	0.08	0.09	0.10
$K \times 10^3$	..	5.62	3.74	2.43	2.30	2.01	1.70	1.46	1.32	1.10

The regular fall in value of K with rise in concentration has the same meaning as in the case of cells 'a' and 'f'. The minimum value of K_1 should be 5.62×10^{-3} , but a higher value is possible. An arbitrary value is given to μ . As explained earlier, $\mu=4$ $[\text{Cd}^{2+}]$ in solutions of cadmium sulphate whether $\text{Cd}[\text{SO}_4]_2^{2-}$ is present or not. Knowing μ , it becomes possible to calculate $[\text{Cd}^{2+}]$, f^{2+} , and f^{2-} . Since $\alpha_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$ is known for the cell, $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$ is calculated. Equation (8) then gives $[\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}]$ and equation (6), $[\text{CdSO}_4]$. Now it becomes possible to calculate

$$K_1 = [\text{Cd}^{2+}] [\text{SO}_4^{2-}] f^{2+} f^{2-} / [\text{CdSO}_4].$$

The arbitrary ionic strength is altered till K_1 becomes equal to the desired figure and then K_2 is calculated from the known corresponding values of $[\text{CdSO}_4]$, $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$, and $[\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}]$. Thus the values of K_2 for different values of $[\text{CdSO}_4]_T$, corresponding to a definite value of K_1 , are calculated. These values of K_1 and K_2 were subjected to the same kind of analysis as in the case of cells 'a' and 'f', but on account of errors in l.j.p. and hence in the values of K_2 , the analysis was not found to be useful. So only rough values of K_1 and K_2 can be found from cells of the type 'b₂' by assuming that the value of K , corresponding to one stage dissociation at the lowest concentration, is the rough value of K_1 and the corresponding value of K_2 will be the rough value of K_2 . The value of K_2 thus determined is given below when $K_1 = 5.62 \times 10^{-3}$.

$[\text{CdSO}_4]_T$...	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.08	0.09	0.10	Mean
$K_2 \times 10^2$...	11.95	9.72	7.67	6.91	6.30	6.28	6.36	7.74

We may now turn to cell 'd'. The values of $\alpha_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$ (NH_4NO_3) are shown in Table IV. An arbitrary value is given to ionic strength and $[\text{Cd}^{2+}]$ calculated from equation (11). Knowing μ , f^{2+} and f^{2-} are found as explained earlier. From the values of f^{2-} and $\alpha_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$, $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$ is found out. The value of $[\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}]$ is then found from equation (10) and $[\text{CdSO}_4]$ from equation (6), and K_1 is calculated. The arbitrary value given to μ is then altered till K_1 assumes the desired value. Corresponding to any value of K_1 , the variation in the values of K_2 becomes very wide because a small percentage error in $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$ on account of error in $\alpha_{\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$ (NH_4NO_3) leads to a much bigger percentage error in $[\text{CdSO}_4]$ and $[\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}]$. Hence the study of this cell is not useful in calculating even rough values of K_1 and K_2 . The values of K_2 , corresponding to $K_1 = 5.62 \times 10^{-3}$, are shown below by way of illustration:

$[\text{CdSO}_4]_T$...	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.03
$[\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4]_T$...	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.03	0.06	0.07
$K_2 \times 10^2$...	16.14	7.28	3.01	11.5	3.93	15.02

Hence if cells of the type (a) and (f) are not available, a reasonably good value of K_1 and K_2 can be obtained from the cells of the type (b₂).

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